

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND CLASSROOM CLIMATE

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Abstract:

The purpose of research is to analyze which level Emotional intelligence's (EQ) dimensions have predicted classroom climate (CC) and to search a relationship between EQ and CC according to secondary school teachers' perceptions. This research in which relational screening model is used is made by quantitative research method and the data has been collected by "Bar-On EQ Scale" and "CC Scale". Data collection tools have been conducted in 224 teachers in public secondary schools in Buca in İzmir. In data analysis, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis were used. According to research's results, there is positive and medium level relationship between EQ's dimensions and CC's dimensions. In addition, EQ is a significant predictor of CC's "relation" and "personal growth/goal orientation" in medium level and "system maintenance and change" in high level.

Keywords: emotion, EQ, emotional intelligence, classroom climate

1. Introduction

Emotional intelligence (EQ) and classroom climate (CC) are two terms that are crucial in success and of good quality life for person, group, team or organizations. EQ is based on personal skills in social life and classroom and organizational environment is based on group interaction. In addition, classroom environment includes basic principles and dimensions of organizational environment but it shows originality of classroom's characteristics structure.

The term "EQ" has started to be worked over 25 years in literature. Being worked in business area in the beginning, the term has later become the centre of interest for educational sciences' teachers. The term "EQ" has started to gain importance

when people discover the truth that no one having high marks in such general academic tests as IQ becomes successful in whole life.

1.1. Emotional Intelligence

Inter-personal and intra-personal intelligences from Gardner's multiple intelligences have underlain EQ. The article "Imagination, cognition and personality" from Salovey and Mayer inspired by Gardner (1999) and Sternberg (1985) is the first study on EQ. In their research, authors has remarked on importance of emotions and differences of average people's perceptions in understanding emotions. This approach has revealed the truth that emotions make people more intelligent and have helped to work on emotions and to manage them effectively. Goleman (1995), basing on those authors, has asserted his work searching EQ theoretically for the first time. After this stage, several researches have been made about developing and evaluating EQ (Goleman, Shapiro, Weisinger, Mayer and Salovey, 1993).

According to Bar-On, basing the approach "EQ" on real life results and effective performance fact, EQ is "competences, abilities and skills not being cognitive and gaining a person success in overcoming with demands and environmental pressure. EQ, identified as an art of using emotions wisely by Weisinger (1998), is an intelligence approach synthesizing an area "intelligence" and "emotion". Goleman (2000: 393), who makes the term "EQ" popular, has defined EQ as an ability to identify his own and others' emotions, to motivate himself, to manage personal and relational emotions effectively. According to Cooper and Sawaf (1998), EQ is an ability to sense everything as a source of people's energy, relationship and influence via emotions' power and quick perception, to understand them and to use them effectively. As considering all those conditions, it is possibly said that EQ is the total of a group of abilities to provide people to come into action by identifying himself and others emotionally as an important factor that determines life success, job success and person's self-management. According to George (2000), executives having high EQ are necessary for succeeding in business life. Executives manage their emotions effectively, loyalty to duty and optimism will increase if executives values employees' belief and emotions. It is seen that executives that perceive their employees' emotions, evaluate them and react properly are more successful, motivate employees better and increase employees' personal achievement. In this context, executives' high-level emotional abilities increase workers' job satisfaction and productivity positively (Savaş, 2012: 140; Şahin, Aydoğan and Yoldaş, 2011: 977). According to Macaluso (2003), executives having high-level EQ have evaluated employees' perspectives, body languages, energies and voice characteristics whereas executives having lower-level EQ concentrate on their duties properly. According to Abraham (1999), executives having high-level EQ have experienced less emotional disharmony and ethic role conflict and they have defeated organizational distrust. Thus, organizational commitment has become high. In current regime, group's superiority and achievement is more important, not personal superior characteristics and achievement. The way that group works together and is successful and productive is about group members' having EQ. Human relations are more

important than employees' cognitive features for companies (Kızıl, 2014: 48). Indeed, thousands research has showed EQ's direct effects on companies while in Barsade's research, senior executives having shared positive and common emotional opinions has gained more profits than companies having executives who have different emotional opinions (Caruso and Salovey, 2007: 37). In addition, a relationship between EQ and IQ is high (Alien, 2000). According to Goleman (2000: 33), emotional intelligence skills have brought synergy with cognitive skills. Those who have overperformed have both intelligences. The more complicated the duty is, the more EQ has gained importance. In that, academic intelligence has remained limited in complicated duties (Goleman, 2000: 49). While in researches, emotional energy has constituted 70% of people's energies (Macaluso, 2003), some authors has asserted that IQ has explained only 10-25% of life success (Hunter, 1986; Sternberg, 1996).

Goleman (1995) has analyzed EQ at two headings: personal and interpersonal competences. Personal competences has comprised of self-awareness in other words, self-evaluating and self-management, self-confidence. Self-awareness has explained people have realized how their emotions have affected themselves and job performance (Goleman, Mckee and Boyatsiz, 2002). Social competences has comprised of such abilities as strong communication, interaction and cooperation, being the source of inspiration, forging closer ties, empathy and teamwork. Among those, empathy needs executives and teachers to comprehend emotional messages, which are hidden in words, and to make out body language understand how people feel by listening people's words carefully (Goleman et al., 2002). Expressing one well and controlling one, independency, adaptability, persistence, compassion, courtesy and respect are among other factors of social competences (Parker, 2004). Accordingly, the ability to understand their own emotions and to understand others' emotions and intentions are main themes in EQ (Schutte, et al., 1998). Self-awareness, self-management and empathy are dimensions that need mastership and are the most important one in leadership (Goleman, Mckee and Boyatsiz, 2002). Mayer, Caruso and Salovey have analyzed EQ in their theory in four dimensions: expressing oneself and others' emotions about nature, language, artwork and perception, using emotions for incorporation and reasoning, understanding, anticipation of emotions and reasons and emotion management. Similarly, Cooper and Sawaf's (1998) model has comprised of four cornerstones: emotional literacy including emotional honesty, emotional energy, emotional feedback, practical intuition; emotional fitness including trust, resiliency, authenticity, renewal; emotional depth including applying integrity, influence without authority, commitment, unique potential and purpose; emotional alchemy including opportunity sensing, reflective time-shifting, intuitive flow, creating the future.

EQ has comprised 5 basic skills and 15 sub-skills in Bar-On's model that creates mainframe of this research; those skills are intrapersonal skills (self-regard, emotional self-awareness, assertiveness, independence, self-actualization), interpersonal skills (empathy, social responsibility, interpersonal relationship), stress management (stress tolerance, impulse control), adaptability (reality testing, flexibility, problem solving), and general mood (optimism, happiness).

In researches being made on principals, inspectors, teachers and students, it has been searched that EQ has affected relationships in schools and job quality. Researches have shown that having high level IQ is not enough to succeed in business life and in private life. Gaining success, producing, finding the most suitable solution for problems is related to progress in EQ. One's EQ progress, therefore, has been beneficial for both oneself and society (Güler, 2006: 1). Several researches such as Yeşilyaprak (2001), Akgül (2011), Adıgüzel (2011), Şahin, Aydoğan and Yoldaş (2011) and Yurdakavuştu (2012) have searched how much EQ has affected such factors as job satisfaction, academic achievement, communication skills, leadership and conflict management. When EQ has been mentioned about teachers, a teacher whose emotional skills are developed and whose EQ level is high has been defined as a person who is self-confident, feels oneself better, motivates oneself, likes learning, is sensible, comprehend situations correctly and thinks creative and emphatic. A teacher having used his/her own abilities in classroom environment has provided healthy communicative environment, which creates positive effects on students (Akgül, 2011: 35). CC has been searched as classroom environment in the context of psycho-social climate in literature.

1.2. Classroom Climate

CC has included such factors as support, respect, trust, sincerity, courtesy, solidarity and cooperation, which reflects organization's psychological structure. In order to gain enough output, teachers need to create a positive CC. In the class in which there have been no negative student behaviors and such behaviors have been solved easily, students feel themselves relax and safe and they canalize their attention to the lessons. CC has been called as atmosphere, environment, ecology and environment terms. The effects of CC on both teachers and students may feel positively or negatively and it even prevents learning.

School and CC has been a psychological reflection of school culture, which comprises of consistent things, institutionalised values, belief systems, norms, ideologies, rituals and customs. CC has reflected such perfections related to psychological conditions as school's social system, attitudes, employee and student's moral, power, control, counselling, support and evaluation structure, program and educational practice, communication expectation, efficiency, responsibility volition, adaptability, competition. It has comprised of such life styles as maintenance, growing and life styles, regularity and security (Adelman and Taylor, 2002). CC is the most important determinant of learning and class behaviors (Fraser, 1998; Freiberg, 1999).

By knowing the importance that they take responsibility for student's achievement, teachers needs to create of high quality life styles, to support social and emotional learning as academic achievement, to provide students to gain their inner motivation in learning and education. Social support, flexibility in targets, participation in decisions, inner motivation, teaching individual problem solutions, creating healthy and attractive physical environment are important factors of CC. Everyone in schools has a duty that contributes to create healthy CC and school's psychologist. Traditional counseling system is not enough in this subject (Adelman and Taylo, 2002). It is

important both what teachers teach, how they teach, what kind of relationship, communication and interaction they have with students, how much they know their students and how much they respond to students' expectations. In those days, in which it is easy to reach the information, teachers' role has increased in interaction with students (Demirbolat, 2000: 37).

CC is a kind of interaction having explained a class qualification and student-teacher relationship among students and a class qualification. Teacher and students both have affected this environment via their behaviors and have been affected by this environment. According to Açıkgöz (2009), Erden (2014), Fraser and Walberg (2005), CC is related to how students feel themselves in class and how teacher and students put into practice educational experiences in learning-teaching progress. Küçükahmet (2000) has defined CC as a place in which the interaction between students and teacher has taken place. Classroom's physical, social and psychological environment has played an important role on occurring this climate.

There have naturally been differences between CC which is created by teachers in classes. Different approaches have been mentioned about explaining CC. Borich has stated that social environment and arranging the class are two key elements of CC (Çakmak, 2003: 25). Social environment is teacher-student relationships, behaviours in class, teacher's expectations on students, rules, lesson presentation arrangement, students' and teacher's visions and opinions about each other (Açıkgöz, 2009; Erden, 2014; Fraser, 1999). A healthy physical environment and classroom organization has positively affected CC. In order to carry out learning, teacher's using suitable material and making necessary physical arrangement has affected CC.

As Açıkgöz (2009) has mentioned, individuals in class has affected on such factors as rules, human relations, communication patterns, norms, physical occasions, leadership styles like all social environment. Major CC creating factors have been sorted as physical environment, affective environment, teacher-student relationship, being model and taking someone as a model (Çakmak, 2003: 26). Teacher-student relationship has affected classroom interaction and CC positively or negatively. Besides "being model" and "taking someone as a model" are among factors which have affected on CC. Teacher's attitudes and behaviours in class have been role model for students and students have learned much behaviour by imitating teacher (Açıkgöz, 2009; Çakmak, 2003: 26; Erden, 2014; Küçükahmet, 2000). Kyriacou has ordered influencing factors in CC as creating an intentional and comfortable learning environment, motivating students, teacher-student relationships, increasing students' self-esteem and class general view (Çakmak, 2003: 27).

1.2.1 CC and Determinants/Variables

Class-organization climate has been occurred those frames: "open climate" referring friendly and sincere relationship, "autonomous climate" referring flexibility on self-management and making decision, "controlled climate" referring allowing to flexibility in a controlled way, "parental climate" referring giving specific importance to friendship and to employees' social needs, "father climate" referring trying doing

something insincerely, “closed climate” referring not being cooperation, attachment feeling, belonging and dominating negligence (Tutar and Altıöz, 2010). Classroom variables have ordered as clarity in rules and expectations, award and encouragement, learning ability, high expectation, student's attendance to lesson, teacher-student relationship, school-parent relationship, group norms, teacher-principal relationship and interaction among themselves (Özden, 2003).

CC model was developed by Moos and Trickett (1987) is comprised of this research's framework. From CC's dimensions, “relation” dimension is related to friendship among teacher and students, students' attendance to lesson and teacher's help for students. “Personal growth/goal orientation” dimension is based on students' competition among each other and understanding the hardship of success. In “system maintenance and change”, teacher provides order and organization, sets up rules clearly and explicitly and follows this, shows how he/she is determinant of practicing the rules and supports students' creative thinking.

1.3. Emotional Intelligence and CC

According to Barineau, teacher as a leader creating a desirable emotional climate has such huge roles as not only completing deficiencies of academic achievement but also dealing with students' out-of-class lives and problems. According to Bradfield, creating a desirable CC and protecting this climate is highly crucial for education and it has been possible for teacher being a member of a group in a social climate to provide a constructive counselling when understanding students' perspectives, providing care and trust environment, understanding hardships, providing trust at necessary place and at necessary time. In addition, the most crucial element having affected on class environment is teacher. What kind of characteristics teacher has, what he/she does, what and how he/she says, what he/she thinks and how he/she behaves have generally affected on students (Sağlam, 2006: 15).

Emotional supportive motivation provides interest, enjoyment and dependence (Curby et al, 2009), less violence (Spratt, 2004), adaptation and increasing academic achievement (Luo, Huang and Najjar, 2007; Pianta, Belsky, Vandergrift, Houts and Morrison, 2008; Rudasill, Gallagher and White, 2010; Ruus et al. 2007). The quality of social and emotional interaction in class has showed class' emotional climate (Pianta et al. 2008). This interaction has included such many elements as teacher's being sensitive to student's needs, being sincere, friendly and respectful, supporting attendance, supporting healthy student-student and student-teacher relationship, avoiding back-breaking discipline and cynicism (Hamre and Pianta, 2007). Teachers who have those characteristics have naturally helped students to improve those skills. Otherwise, there has occurred mistrustful and disrespectful environment instead of a loyalty between students and teacher. In such environment, teacher's moving without understanding effectively what they say and how they feel, interacting with students without controlling their own emotions has triggered off students' undesirable and backbreaking behaviour. In a word, there has occurred a negative climate in class (Gayle and Chapman, 2012).

Teacher's close and consistent behaviours towards students have contributed a positive learning process. In such environment, student has developed such positive emotions as adaptation and love, respect, belonging, loyalty and performance (Brackett, Reyes, Rivers, Elbertson and Salovey, 2011, Furrer and Skinner, 2003; Klem and Connell, 2004; Murray and Greenberg, 2001; Osterman, 2000; Wentzel, 1998). According to Gayle and Chapman (2012), classroom's emotional climate has an important effect on learning. Besides, according to Caine, Caine, McClintic and Klimek'e (2008), who have an important place on brain-based learning, emotion and social phenomenon are among learning's 12 principles.

Students' EQ competence in schools the relationship among such variables as social skills, education expectation, academic achievement by Adıgüzel (2011), Adıyaman (2010), Korkmaz (2008), Lyons and Schneider (2005), Özerbaş (2004), Dağlı (2006), Köse (2009), Sheykhani, Jabari and Rajeswari (2014), Tufan (2011), Üzel and Hangül (2011), Yurdakavuştu (2012), the relationship between teacher's EQ level and such many different variables as conflict management, anger control, solving problem, social responsibility, performance, transformational leadership and communication skills by Arlı, Altunay and Yalçınkaya (2011), Bardach (2008), Baltacı and Demir (2012), Drew (2006), Fayombo (2012), Güler (2006), Akgül (2011), Kızıl (2012), Weinberg (2004) has been analysed. While Özdemir and Özdemir (2007) has searched the relationship between EQ and conflict management, Kızıl (2012) stress coping skills, and Nazlı (2013) problem solving skills, Şahin, Aydoğdu and Yoldaş (2011) job satisfaction, and Acar-Tekin (2001) leadership.

Many researches have made on CC, for instance, the relationship between CC and academic achievement by Allen (1986), Baek and Choi (2002), Bourke ve Smith (1989), Kealoha (2006); teacher's characteristics and CC by Walberg (1967); individualist learning by Walberg and Anderson (1968), Cheng (1994) teacher leadership and performance in addition to Ching-jun Lia (2009), DiLalla and Mullineaux (2008), Fraser and Fisher (1982) and Nair and Fisher (1999) have confirmed students' perceptions of CC.

In Turkey, Karşı (2012) and Kızıllan (2011) has researched the relationship between CC and academic achievement, Aslan (2011) teacher leadership, Asrağ (2009) native language, Künkül (2008) student's attendance, Ceylan (2007) school life quality, loyalty to friends and teacher's communication skills, Karşı (2012) academic achievement; Erdoğan (2009) project-based learning, and Koç (2007) class interaction, critical thinking, the effects of active learning on reading comprehension.

In recent years, the importance of EQ, which is focus of interest for several people and institutions from education and from other areas, has gradually increased. In this respect, independent researches related to problem solving, conflict management and academic achievement for determining the situation, which is about teacher and students' EQ level in schools, has been encountered. Only Coetzee and Jansen (2008) have discussed the relationship between EQ and CC. In Turkey, there is no research on this subject. In this research, searching on the relationship between EQ and CC is important and it has been the first research on the effects of EQ on CC in Turkey.

1.4. Objectives

The purpose of the research is to analyze which level EQ's dimensions have predicted CC and to search the relationship between EQ and CC according to secondary school teachers' perceptions.

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

In this research, which is on the relationship between secondary school teachers' EQ and CC relational screening model has been used. Relational screening model is a research model that is aimed to determine the change existence or the level between two or more variables. The relationship that is found by screening cannot be interpreted as cause-result relationship; yet by giving some clues about this aspects, knowing the situation of a variable and forecasting the other can cause positive results (Karasar, 2011: 82). In this research that is relational screening model, EQ has been determined as independent and CC has been determined as dependent variables.

2.2. Participants

The population of this research, which was made in 2014-2015 educational year, has comprised of 1100 secondary school teachers who has worked in Buca in İzmir. Research's sample has been chosen stratified sampling to conclude with schools having every social economic level and achievement level. Participants in those groups have been obtained via random sampling method; 224 teachers working on 8 secondary schools has constituted the sample. It has been given attention that the sample has represented 10% of population.

2.3. Data Collection Tools

In collecting data, "Bar-On EQ Scale (Bar-On EQS)" by Bar-On and "Classroom Climate Scale (CCS)" by Moos and Trickett (1987) has been used.

2.3.1 Bar-On EQ Scale

In scaling EQ, Bar-On EQS on which Bar-On has made his validity and reliability research has been used. Bar-On EQS developed by Bar-On has been translated into Turkish and adapted by Acar-Tekin (2001). Fourth lecturer again translated the scale, which was translated into Turkish by three English lecturers, into English. The original and the translation of the scale have been compared with each other. Expressions that have caused the possibility of misunderstanding have been revised. In scale's pilot scheme, 5 bank managers and 2 assistant managers have been conducted via face to face meeting method and expressions' content validity has been tested. From 133 items in scale, 15 items that were in no dimensions but showed participant's tendency to solve the test have been removed. After meetings with experts, ambiguous expressions, double-barrelled words and similar expressions have been removed from the scale. So, 87-item-scale comprising of "intrapersonal skills", "interpersonal skills", "adaptability", "stress management", "general mood" dimensions. There have been 29 items in

“intrapersonal skills”, 18 items “interpersonal skills”, 15 items in “adaptability”, 12 items in “general mood” dimensions (Akgül, 2011: 75). Scale's Cronbach's alpha coefficients were found to be .66 for “intrapersonal skills” dimension, .54 for “interpersonal skills” dimension, .52 for “adaptability” dimension, .39 for “stress management” dimension and .44 for “general mood” dimension. Scale's general reliability has been found .80.

2.3.2 Classroom Climate Scale

Moos and Trickett (1987) have developed “CCS” in order to scale CC in secondary schools and academies. In this scale, which comprised of 90 items, there are true and false boxes opposite every item. Scale's Turkish translation and reliability study has been made by Tüter (1989). In adaptation, several experts knowing both languages (Turkish and English) have worked on this study. In Turkish form that has comprised of 90 items, retranslation method has been used. “CCS” has comprised of three dimensions: “relation” dimension with 30 items, “personal growth/goal orientation” dimension with 20 items and “system maintenance and change” dimension with 40 items. The reliability of the scale has made with Richardson 20 method by Moos and Trickett (1987). The reliability studies in Turkey has implemented by Tüter (1989) and scale's Cronbach's alpha coefficients were found to be .76 in “relation” dimension, .54 in “personal growth/goal orientation”, .83 in “system maintenance and change” dimension. Scale's general reliability has been .84.

In order to conduct data collection tools, it has been got permission from İzmir Provincial Directorate for National Education and Ethical Committee. The scales have taken to the schools in which the research has made by hand with the permission paper. In schools, after meeting principals, the scales have been conducted to volunteer teachers by explaining the data collection tools. In schools, which have many teachers, in order to increase the participation, the scales have been delivered to the schools by researcher. In the end of following time, researcher has received the scales. In 2014-2015 educational year, 224 scales (64%) from the scales which has been made to 350 teachers in 8 public secondary schools in Buca in İzmir has been analyzed, all of them has seen to be valid and has evaluated.

2.4. Data Analysis

To analyze the data of the research, arithmetic mean and standard deviation were checked by using SPSS 15 statistics analysis program. In order to calculate the level of prediction and relation between two variables, Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) and multiple regression analysis were used. Significance level has been stated as $p < 0.05$.

3. Findings

First, the relationship between EQ and CC has been examined. Accordingly, correlation (r) analysis about this relationship has been showed in Table 1:

Table 1: Correlations between Secondary School Teachers' EQ and CC.

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.Intrapersonal Skills	1	.82*	.79*	.60*	.82*	.54*	.45*	.57*
2.Interpersonal Skills		1	.79*	.69*	.83*	.59*	.40*	.67*
3.Adaptability			1	.69*	.80*	.60*	.46*	.59*
4.Stress Management				1	.63*	.42*	.18*	.40*
5.General Mood					1	.57*	.35*	.65*
6. Relation						1	.50*	.74*
7.Personal Growth/Goal Orientation							1	.45*
8.System Maintenance and Change								1

According to Table 1, there was a positive, medium level and significant relationship between teachers' emotional intelligence and CC. There is a positive, medium level and significant relationship between "relation" and "system maintenance and change" from dependent variables and "intrapersonal skills" (r=.54), "interpersonal skills" (r=.59), "adaptability" (r=.60), "stress management" (r=.42) and "general mood" (r=.57) from predictive variables. There is a low positive relationship between "personal growth/goal orientation" from dependent variables and "stress management" (r=.18) from predictive variables and there is a medium positive relationship between all other predictive dimensions and "personal growth/goal orientation" dimension.

Second, regression analysis on the effects of EQ on "relation" dimension has been given in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of Regression Analysis Predicting Scores of EQ on "Relation" Dimension

Variable	B	SH _B	β	t	P	Dual r	Partial r
Stable	55.511	5.833	-	9.516	.000	-	-
Intrapersonal Skills	-.418	.158	-.395	-2.636	.007	-.134	-.176
Interpersonal Skills	.104	.202	.071	.514	.033	.026	.035
Adaptability	.366	.196	.240	1.868	.000	.095	.126
Stress Management	-.613	.193	-.315	-3.175	.000	-.162	-.211
General Mood	-.028	.235	-.015	-.119	.824	-.006	-.008

R=.661 R²=.436 F=28.011 p=.000

In Table 2, there has seen a positive medium level and significant relationship between "relation" dimension and EQ's overall dimensions ("intrapersonal skill", "interpersonal skills", "adaptability", "stress management", "general mood")(R=.66, R²=.43, p<.05). Those five dimensions have explained 44% of CC's total variance. According to standardized regression coefficient (β), the importance degree of predictive variables on "relation" dimension has ranged as "adaptability", "interpersonal skills", "general mood", "stress management" and "intrapersonal skills". According to the t-test results

of regression coefficient's significance, "adaptability" ($R=.61$, $R^2=.37$, $p<.05$), "interpersonal skills" ($R=.58$, $R^2=.33$, $p<.05$), "stress management" ($R=.40$, $R^2=.16$, $p<.05$) and "intrapersonal skills" ($R=.53$, $R^2=.28$, $p<.05$) dimensions are found as medium level and significant predictors of "relation" dimension.

Third, regression analysis on the effects of EQ on "personal growth/goal orientation" dimension has been given in Table 3.

Table 3: Results of Regression Analysis Predicting Scores of EQ on "Personal Growth/Goal Orientation" Dimension

Variable	B	SH _B	β	t	P	Dual r	Partial r
Stable	50.248	4.295	-	11.699	.000	-	-
Intrapersonal Skills	-.418	.177	-.045	-.277	.782	-.015	-.019
Interpersonal Skills	.104	.149	.020	.132	.895	.007	.009
Adaptability	.366	.144	.533	3.803	.000	.212	.250
Stress Management	-.613	.142	-.635	-5.858	.000	-.326	-.370
General Mood	-.028	.080	-.294	-2.176	.031	-.121	-.146

R=.572 R²=.327 F=17.610 p=.000

In Table 3, there has seen a medium significant relationship between "personal growth/goal orientation" dimension and EQ's overall dimensions ("intrapersonal skill", "interpersonal skills", "adaptability", "stress management", "general mood") ($R=.57$, $R^2=.32$, $p<.05$). Those five dimensions have explained 33% of CC's total variance. According to standardized regression coefficient (β), the importance degree of predictive variables on "personal growth/goal orientation" dimension has ranged as "adaptability", "interpersonal skills", "general mood", "stress management" and "intrapersonal skills". According to the t-test results of regression coefficient's significance, "adaptability" ($R=.43$, $R^2=.18$, $p<.05$), "stress management" ($R=.08$, $R^2=.07$, $p<.05$) and "general mood" ($R=.32$, $R^2=.10$, $p<.05$) dimensions are found as medium level and significant predictors of "personal growth/goal orientation" dimension.

Finally, regression analysis on the effects of EQ on "system maintenance and change" dimension has been given in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of Regression Analysis Predicting Scores of EQ on "System Maintenance and Change" Dimension

Variable	B	SH _B	β	t	P	Dual r	Partial r
Stable	75.525	6.293	-	12.002	.000	-	-
Intrapersonal Skills	-.359	.128	-.286	-2.802	.006	-.130	-.186
Interpersonal Skills	1.074	.177	.619	6.065	.000	.281	.380
Adaptability	.457	.179	.252	2.560	.011	.119	.171
Stress Management	-.592	.160	-.256	-3.696	.000	-.171	-.243
General Mood	.772	.201	.342	-3.835	.000	.178	.251

R=.730 R²=.532 F=49.642 p=.000

In Table 4, there has seen a medium significant relationship between "system maintenance and change" dimension and EQ's overall dimensions ("intrapersonal skill", "interpersonal skills", "adaptability", "stress management", "general mood")

($R=.73$, $R^2=.53$, $p<.05$). Those five dimensions have explained 53% of CC's total variance. According to standardized regression coefficient (β), the importance degree of predictive variables on "system maintenance and change" dimension has ranged as "interpersonal skills", "general mood", "adaptability", "stress management" and "intrapersonal skills". According to the t-test results of regression coefficient's significance, "intrapersonal skills" ($R=.56$, $R^2=.31$, $p<.05$), "interpersonal skills" ($R=.67$, $R^2=.45$, $p<.05$), "adaptability" ($R=.61$, $R^2=.37$, $p<.05$), "stress management" ($R=.38$, $R^2=.14$, $p<.05$) and "general mood" ($R=.64$, $R^2=.42$, $p<.05$) dimensions are found as high level and significant predictors of "system maintenance and change" dimension.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

The research has been designed to reveal the importance and significance of EQ on CC and the relationship between EQ and CC. Being nearly high level relationship between EQ's "intrapersonal skills", "interpersonal skills", "adaptability", "general mood" dimensions and CC's "system maintenance and change" dimension is one of those. This finding has shown consistency in opinions that employees having high EQ has experienced less professional burnout and more job satisfaction (Güllüce and İşcan, 2010; Psilopanagiotti, Anagnostopoulos, Mourtou, and Niakas, 2012; Savaş, 2012; Şahin, Aydoğan and Yoldaş, 2011). Since, teachers who have high EQ and haven't experienced burnout, in other words have been energetic and ambitious for their job have made the effort to develop and protect a regular classroom environment in which effective learning and teaching has come true. There has been nearly high-level relationship between EQ's "intrapersonal skills", "interpersonal skills", "adaptability", "general mood" dimensions and CC's "relation" and "personal growth/goal orientation" dimension. When the theory has discussed about intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligences (Bar-On, 1995, 1997; Gardner, 1983; Goleman, 1995, 2000), this result has confirmed the theory. In other words, it can be said that those results is parallel to theory's essence. In other words, teachers having high EQ can create positive, coherent relational-social satisfaction environment.

There has found a low-level relationship between EQ's "stress management" and CC's "personal growth/goal orientation". Medium-level stress is a preferred situation to direct multilateral thinking and to study for gaining success (Ertekin, 1993; Sanders, 1983). In this content, managing completely stress can be a reducing factor on development and success. In this sense, low-level relationship can be acceptable. In addition, from the results, it has been understood that there has been other factors having explained success, development and orientation skills and searching those factors has benefitted.

EQ's overall dimensions have significantly predicted "system maintenance and change". In other words, EQ is an important factor on have an integrity and persistence in such subjects as obeying the classroom rules, keeping to subjects and lessons, thinking and producing ideas differently in flexibility and independence, becoming organized easily and adhering to discipline and organization. In this context, the

success has increased in well-organized classroom. Bardach (2008), Drew, (2006) and Fayombo (2012) have drawn attention to the positive effects of EQ on success and performance. Besides, EQ's "adaptation", "interpersonal skills", "stress management", "general mood" and "intrapersonal skills" has explained CC's "relation" and "personal growth/goal orientation" in medium level. In parallel, Çetinkaya and Alparşlan (2011) has emphasized that EQ is an influencing factor in communication skills. Accordingly, coherent teachers who having social and personal skills, positive general mood and high stress management has positively affected on CC especially on controlling and improving the classroom organization and managing relationships in harmony.

Supporting this result, Baltacı and Demir (2012) has stated that EQ has been an important variable, which helps anger management. When the importance of anger management in relationships has predicated on, it can be easily understood how much managing teacher's anger in classroom have been crucial in a positive classroom environment. Similarly, Karabulutlu, Yılmaz and Yurttaş (2011) and İşmen (2001) has drawn attention to EQ's increasing problem solving skills. When help, passion and humor has been taken into consideration in positive CC, Sheykhani, Jabari and Rajeswari (2014) has determined the relationship between EQ and social responsibility; Hamarta, Deniz and Saltalı'nın (2009) has determined the relationship between EQ and passion and humor. It is obvious that class which has humor, passion and cooperation has provides positive climate.

In this content, teachers having high EQ have significantly contributed positive CC that is crucial in students' success and school's efficiency (Cheng, 1994; Karşı, 2012; Kızıllhan, 2011).

5. Recommendations

By drawing attention to creating CC positively, the opportunities has been provided creating interactive environment and EQ developmental training to teachers and precautions against factors in limiting their EQ have been taken. Courses, seminar and in service training has been arranged to teach techniques which improve EQ and creating skills in positive climate, increase the awareness of facts and concepts about CC. Besides, the relationship between EQ and CC has been analyzed in different variables and similar subjects has discussed in primary schools, high schools and academies.

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